

MICRO-MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF FRACTURE IN

BRITTLE FIBER COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Ming S. Chang
Brunswick Corporation
Skokie, Illinois 60076

The purpose of this study is to investigate the stress and deformation fields and possible fracture modes in a composite when the first weakest fiber breaks during loading. A simplified composite model, consisting of strong laminates embedded in a soft matrix, is presented for the study. By using finite-element analysis, stress and deformation fields of the model under uni-axial tensile stresses along the broken laminate in the composite has been used to describe the load transfer from the broken laminate to the matrix. Possible failure modes are discussed by examining the axial and transverse stress concentrations around the laminate crack tip.

Introduction

Composite materials, containing high strength filaments or fibers in soft matrix, are of interest for structural applications where high stiffness to weight and ultimate strength to weight ratios are required (1). Unfortunately, most high strength fibers are brittle, and therefore they are sensitive to surface flaws and other defects. This fact accounts for the scatter in their strength (2). Consider what happens to a bundle of fibers when a matrix is added. When load is applied, at some stress level the first weakest fiber breaks. The load in the broken fiber is transmitted to adjacent fibers causing them to be overstressed locally. The interfacial shear stress acts on the broken fiber and its axial stress increases from zero to the average stress in the composite (3,4). It is the purpose of this study to investigate the influence of this fracture process on the stress and deformation fields in the composite.

A review of the literature indicates that it is difficult to use the method of classical stress analysis (5) to deal with the fracture behavior in the composites which are considered as heterogeneous systems. This paper utilizes the techniques of finite-element analysis (6) to study the influence of the fracture process on the stress and deformation fields in the composite subjected to uniaxial load.

A simplified, two-dimensional model consisting of hard laminates embedded in a soft matrix is presented for this study (Fig. 1). The analysis accounts for the influence of non-homogeneity in the composite and the breakage of the laminate.

Analytical Models and Methods of Analysis

The finite-element analysis was employed to overcome many of the well-known limitations of the solutions based on the classical theories of elasticity.

The analysis was made of the simplified composite model shown in Fig. 1. Because the X and Y axes are lines of symmetry, only one quarter of the model was analyzed. The resulting finite element representation is shown in Fig. 2. Loading conditions were modelled by imposing displacement boundaries in the analysis. The displacements on the boundaries are

$$\begin{aligned}u &= 0 \text{ at } X=0, \\v &= 0 \text{ at } Y=0, \text{ and} \\v &= \Delta \text{ at } Y= \pm a,\end{aligned}$$

in which u = displacement in the X direction,
 v = displacement in the Y direction,
 Δ = displacement on the boundary,
 a = half length of the composite model.

In addition, the broken laminate was accounted for by releasing the supports normal to the crack surface (Fig. 2).

The composite model was given the dimensions of 10 in. axial length, 11 in. width and 0.25 in. thickness. Moduli for the reinforcement laminates and soft matrix were taken as 60×10^6 psi and 10×10^6 psi respectively. Poisson ratios used were 0.2 for the laminates and 0.34 for the matrix.

The analysis was performed by using STRUDL-II (7) finite-element analysis program with the aid of the electronic digital computer. Linear-Strain-Triangle (LST) elements formulation (6) was chosen for this analysis. Stress and deformation fields were computed for the fracture model at the composite strain of 0.04% under uniaxial loading.

Analytical Results

For the given fracture model, with the selected mechanical property constants, stress and deformation fields were obtained.

Tensile axial stresses (σ_{yy}) for the fracture model along $Y=0.00$ in. are shown in Fig. 3. It is seen that stress concentration exists in the adjacent laminate near the laminate crack. This indicates that the breakage of additional laminate is likely if the composite is further loaded.

Transverse stresses (σ_{xx}) along $Y=0.00$ in. are shown in Fig. 4. Compressive stress fields exist behind the crack tip in this fracture process. These compressive stresses are induced as the broken laminate springs back. The stress concentration of σ_{xx} at the interface of the matrix and the adjacent laminate is regarded to be responsible for the debonding in the composite model.

Shear stresses (σ_{xy}) and axial tensile stresses (σ_{yy}) along the broken laminate and matrix interface ($X=0.50$ in.) are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 respectively. σ_{yy} increases from zero as σ_{xy} acting on the broken laminate decreases. The transfer of the load from matrix to the broken laminate is seen from these stress variations.

Stress distributions of σ_{yy} and σ_{xx} along $Y=4.00$ in. are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 respectively. Tensile axial stresses are found to be smaller in the broken laminate; this indicates that the load transfer mentioned above is not completed.

Crack opening displacements (COD) for this fracture model are shown in Fig. 9. It is observed that the broken laminate springs back after it fractures.

Conclusions and Discussions

A simplified two-dimensional composite model, consisting of strong laminates embedded in a soft matrix, has been used to study the fracture behavior in a composite which contains brittle fibers. This demonstrates that a qualitative micro-mechanical analysis in the composite mentioned above is possible by using finite-element analysis.

The sudden fracture of the weakest laminate in the composite causes axial tensile stress concentration in the surrounding matrix and its adjacent laminate. This stress concentration is responsible for the crack propagation into the matrix and adjacent laminate.

Behind the laminate crack tip, compressive transverse stresses are induced because of the spring-back of the broken laminate. The tensile transverse stress concentration at the interface of the matrix and the adjacent laminate is regarded as responsible for the debonding in the composite model.

The variations of interfacial shear stresses and the tensile stresses along the broken laminate has demonstrated the load transfer from the neighboring matrix to the broken laminate.

The failure modes are highly affected by the matrix/laminate bond strength and mechanical properties of both matrix and laminate. Therefore, further fracture behavior depends on the knowledge of bond strength of matrix/laminate, mechanical properties of both matrix and laminate and stress redistribution as the crack propagates.

Since matrix and laminate have much difference in their mechanical properties, special care should be taken for their interface. It may be represented by a thin layer of interfacial elements for which special mechanical properties are assigned.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to express his appreciation to Professor R. Gallagher of Cornell University for his assistance and Dr. E. Scala of Cortland Line Company for his encouragement.

References

1. Broutman, L. J., and Krock, R. H., "Modern Composite Materials," Addison-Wesley, Reading, Mass., 1967.
2. Rosen, B. W., "Mechanics of Composite Strengthening Fiber Composite Materials," American Society for Metals, Metals Park, Ohio, 1965.
3. Tetelman, A. S., "Fracture Processes in Fiber Composite Materials," Composite Materials: Testing and Design, ASTM STP 460, American Society for Testing Materials, 1969, pp. 473-502.
4. Zweben, C., "Tensile Failure Analysis of Fibrous Composite," Journal, AIAA, Vol. 6, No. 12, Dec. 1968.
5. Cooper, G. A., and Kelly, A., "Tensile Properties of Fiber-Reinforced Metals: Fracture Mechanics," Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, Vol. 15, pp. 279-297.
6. Zienkiewicz, O. C., "The Finite Element Method in Structural and Continuum Mechanics," McGraw Hill Book Co., N.Y., 1967.
7. Logcher, R. D., Connor, J. and Ferrante, A. J., "ICES STRUDL-II. The Structural Design Language," MIT Dept. of Civil Engineering Research Report R-68-92, June 1969.

1. Simplified Composite Model.

2. Finite Element Representation.

3. Axial Stresses Along Y=0.00 in.

4. Transverse Stresses Along Y=0.00 in.

5. Interfacial Shear Stresses Along $X=0.50$ in.

6. Axial Stresses in Broken Laminate ($X=0.50$ in.).

7. Axial Stresses Along Y=4.00 in.

8. Transverse Stresses Along Y=4.00 in.

9. Crack Opening Displacements.